

Carbon-13 NMR Chemical Shifts of some Podophyllum Lignans and Analogues

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Carbon-13 nmr chemical shifts of a number of podophyllum lignans, podophyllotoxin, 4'-demethylpodophyllotoxin, podophyllotoxone, desoxypodophyllotoxin and their derivatives have been determined. The derivatives include 1-naphthol, quinone, diol and tetrahydrofuran compounds.

Podophyllotoxin (1) and its analogues belonging to podophyllum lignans have been used as antitumor agents¹⁻³ and cytostatic spindle poisons⁴. Some of the podophyllotoxin derivatives, etoposide and teniposide have found useful clinical application as anticancer drugs⁵. Analogues of 1 without lactone ring are found to be still antimitotic⁶. In our continued work in the field of lignans⁷, we report here the carbon-13 chemical shifts data for podophyll-

lotoxin (1), 4'-demethylpodophyllotoxin (2) and some of the chemically transformed products of podophyllotoxin, viz. podophyllotoxin acetate (3), podophyllotoxone (4), desoxypodophyllotoxin (5), 3',4'-demethyl-3',4'-dioxy-podophyllotoxin (6), 4-hydroxy-3-hydroxymethyl-6,7-methylenedioxy-1-(3',4',5'-trimethoxyphenyl)-2-naphthoic acid γ -lactone (7), 2a,3a-bishydroxymethyl-4-hydroxy-6,7-methylenedioxy-1-(3',4',5'-trimethoxyphenyl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalene (8) and 4-hydroxy-6,7-methylenedioxy-1-(3',4',5'-trimethoxyphenyl)-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphtho[2,3-c]-furan (9). As podophyllum lignans are biologically active, their carbon-13 nmr spectral data will be important addition to the literature.

Results and Discussion

The carbon-13 nmr shifts of the compounds 1-9 are enumerated in Table 1. The C-2a lactone carbonyl carbons appear in the region of δ 170 ppm, but C-2a carbons of the alcohol (8) and the tetrahydrofuran derivative (9) appear near 62 ppm. The chemical shifts of C-6 and C-7 carbons, which are aromatic as well as attached to the methylenedioxy group, occur mainly at the same position near δ 147 ppm. Similar results are observed in cases of C-5 and C-8 carbons, *ortho* to the methylenedioxy group and their signals appear around δ 170 ppm and also for the quaternary carbons C-4a and C-8a where two groups of carbons display peaks in the region δ 128.0-132.3 ppm except for compound 7. Here C-4a carbon belongs to part of the 1-naphthol moiety and the upfield shift at δ 119.1 ppm is due to the presence of *ortho*-hydroxy group at C-4. The chemical shifts of C-3a carbons are displayed near δ 70 ppm except for the compound 8, where it appears at δ 63.4 ppm due to the presence of hydroxymethyl group. The C-4 methine carbons of most of the compounds are attached to hydroxyl functionalities and absorb near 72 ppm except for the compounds 4, 5 and 7, where C-4 carbons appear at δ 192.4, 32.8 and 140.4 ppm respectively. The chemical shifts of C-1 and C-2 carbons in most of the compounds are displayed in the threshold of 45 ppm, and those belonging to compound 7 show up at δ 130.3 and 119.0 ppm respectively, as they form a part of the aromatic system. Similarly, while C-3 carbons for most of the compounds appear near δ 40 ppm, that of 7 appears at δ 118.6 ppm. The chemical shift of C-3 carbon of desoxypodophyll-

1 R¹=H, R²=Me, X=O

2 R¹=R²=H, X=O

3 R¹=COCH₃, R²=Me, X=O

9 R¹=H, R²=Me, X=H₂

4 X=O

5 X=H₂

6

7

8

TABLE I—¹³C NMR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1-9 (CHEMICAL SHIFTS IN δ , ppm)

Carbon nos.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
C-1	44.4	44.2	43.7	44.7	43.5	43.2	130.3	42.1	44.5
C-2	44.9	45.1	45.5	46.0	47.2	44.3	119.0	47.4	47.3
C-2a	174.6	174.6	171.3	172.8	174.7	174.7	169.6	62.1	61.8
C-3	41.0	40.9	38.6	43.6	32.5	42.3	118.6	40.7	43.4
C-3a	71.3	71.3	71.3	66.8	71.8	70.7	68.0	63.4	68.5
C-4	72.0	72.1	73.6	192.4	32.8	71.0	140.4	69.8	77.7
C-4a	131.6	131.3	132.3	128.0	128.0	131.7	119.1	132.3	129.5
C-5	106.8	106.7	108.2	105.3	107.6	106.3	103.7	106.9	107.9
C-6	147.5	147.5	148.1	147.9	146.5	146.5	150.0	146.7	147.7
C-7	147.5	147.3	148.1	141.3	146.5	146.5	148.7	146.7	146.3
C-8	109.5	109.5	109.6	109.8	110.2	109.2	107.2	108.4	109.8
C-8a	131.6	131.6	132.3	128.0	128.1	131.2	130.3	131.8	129.5
C-1'	135.2	135.2	134.7	132.0	130.4	144.9	139.8	137.4	131.6
C-2'	109.2	109.3	106.9	108.4	108.1	128.3	107.3	107.4	107.0
C-3'	152.9	153.0	152.6	152.9	152.3	—	152.9	152.4	153.1
C-4'	136.7	131.9	134.7	137.6	136.1	—	134.6	136.4	138.4
C-5'	152.9	153.0	152.6	152.9	152.3	147.4	152.9	152.4	153.1
C-6'	109.2	109.3	106.9	108.4	108.1	134.9	107.3	107.4	107.0
OCH ₂ O	101.6	101.5	101.5	102.8	100.9	101.0	101.8	100.6	100.9
3',5'-OMe	55.8	56.5	56.1	55.8	56.0	55.9	56.1	56.0	56.2
4'-OMe	59.8	—	60.6	59.8	60.4	—	61.0	60.6	60.2

lotoxin (5) shows up relatively upfield at 32.5 ppm. This may be due to the absence of oxygen functionality at the adjacent carbon (C-4). The chemical shifts of methylenedioxy carbons are displayed at δ 101 ppm.

The chemical shifts of the aromatic carbons in the pendant ring are in parity to the rules for the substituents effects⁸ on the aromatic carbons; C-3' and C-5' carbons attached to the methoxyl groups appear near δ 153 ppm, whereas C-4' carbons due to the presence of two *ortho*-methoxyl groups are observed relatively upfield near δ 135 ppm. In compound 2, the chemical shift of C-4' appears slightly upfield as it is attached to a hydroxyl group instead of methoxyl group. The carbon-13 signals of C-1' carbons are displayed in the range δ 130–140 ppm, whereas those of C-2' and C-6' carbons remain near δ 108–109 ppm. However in quinone (6), C-1', C-2', C-5' and C-6' carbons absorb at δ 144.9, 128.3, 147.4 and 134.9 ppm respectively.⁹

Experimental

The carbon-13 nmr spectra were recorded on Bruker AM-300L and Varian CFT-20 spectrometers operating at 75.47 and 20.1 MHz respectively in FT mode, and equipped with ASPECT 300 and VDM 620L computers respectively. The compounds were submitted to noise decoupling, single frequency off-resonance decoupling (SFORD) and distortionless enhanced by polarisation transfer (DEPT) to establish the carbon shifts and the degree of protonations. The samples were run in acetone-d₆, CDCl₃ and DMSO-d₆ as solvents as well as internal lock and internal reference. The spectra of compounds 1 and 2 were measured in acetone-d₆ and that of 6 in DMSO-d₆, whereas rest of the compounds were measured in CDCl₃.

All solutions were *ca.* 5–15% (w/v) in concentration. The chemical shifts reported are in δ (ppm) downfield from TMS; $\delta_{\text{TMS}} = \delta_{\text{acetone-d}_6} + 29.2$ ppm, $\delta_{\text{TMS}} = \delta_{\text{CDCl}_3} + 76.9$ ppm and $\delta_{\text{TMS}} = \delta_{\text{DMSO-d}_6} + 39.6$ ppm. The spectra were run with sweep widths 4000 and 15000 Hz, pulse width 6 and 3 μ s and approximately 2 s pulse repetition time.

Podophyllotoxin (1) and 4'-demethylpodophyllotoxin (2) were isolated from ethanolic extract of roots of the plant *Podophyllum emodi* (Berberidaceae) by chromatographic separation over silica gel (B.D.H., 60–120 mesh). Methanolic chloroform (2%) eluent furnished 1, whereas 4% methanolic chloroform eluent yielded 2. Podophyllotoxin (1) was converted into podophyllotoxin acetate (3) upon refluxing with acetic anhydride in the presence of pyridine. Manganese dioxide¹⁰ oxidised podophyllotoxin to podophyllotoxone (4). It was transformed into thioketal by means of ethan-1,2-dithiol and this upon desulphurisation with Raney nickel (W2) in refluxing ethanol afforded desoxypodophyllotoxin (5). Again oxidation of podophyllotoxin with nitric acid-acetic acid mixture¹¹ at 0° furnished orthoquinone (6). Aromatisation of podophyllotoxone (4) by selenium dioxide¹⁰ in refluxing acetic acid resulted in the formation of the 1-naphthol derivative (7). Podophyllotoxin was reduced to the diol (8) by reaction with lithium aluminium hydride. The diol (8) upon dehydration in the presence of dry dimethyl sulphoxide¹² at 90° for 12 h afforded the tetrahydrofuran derivative (9).

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